

(The light of the rulers regarding what is best for them and on them) ضياء الحكام فيما لهم وعليهم من الأحكم

also known as "Dhiya' al-Hukkam fima lahum wa alaihim."

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Law, Arabic, Text, Language, Islamic Traditions

The book was prepared as a guide to the judges on the pattern of Islamic adjudication that originates from the Islamic precepts and guidance of the Prophet (SAW). The text begins with the principles of migration, followed by the necessity for the appointment of a leader of a group Muslim community, where certain obligations are set on him concerning his subjects, among whom lieutenant and assistants are selected to render administrative roles in the state, such as judges, Imams, and their likes. Subsequently, principles of public services are analyzed to direct them on a better manner of public services within the state. Other topics glanced at the concept and principles of Islamic Jihad (Warfare) and the rest of the mechanism of the Islamic political system and administrative strategies of the Islamic state.

Date Range: 1767 BCE - 1828 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: عبدالله بن فوديو (1804). ضياء الحكام فيما لهم و عليهم. دار العربية. بيروت لبنان

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://waamd.lib.berkeley.edu/titles/2365?query=Reform&fieldName=subject>

– Source 1 Description: West African Arabic Manuscript Database.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP535-1-2-25-1>

– Source 1 Description: Kitab an nasabi by Sheikh Abdullahi bin Fodio. Endangered Archives Programme. British Library.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: White paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

- ↳ Temple
 - No
- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Bookshops.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
– No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
– No
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 18000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 20000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

–Number: 18000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Migration, Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

–Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is awarded in heaven.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is directed towards the entire non-Muslims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The text centered on the legal adjudication of the principles of the Islamic Shari'ah.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text was designed to dictate the activities of the judiciary.

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: The text established execution for those who killed others unjustly.

↳ Exile?

– Yes

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: One hundred lashes are determined for the unmarried fornicators.

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: The obligatory charitable (Zakat) amount is collected by force from the defaulters.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

Notes: Eid al-Kabir and Eid al-Fitr festivals.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 10000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: The pilgrimage is obligatory for those having means and strength.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The group unanimously accepted Arabic as the language of the afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Bathing, Shrouding, Funeral prayer and Burial.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: Creation of the universe.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Can reward
– Yes
- ↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: Creation of the Universe.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme High God communicates through the Messengers.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: The communication is done through the Messengers.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: Dream.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Supernatural beings are aware of other non-human creatures.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Mysterious movement from one place to another.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery
– Yes
Notes: He made adultery a prohibited act.

↳ Incest
– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
– Yes

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
– Yes
Notes: A reward is given for legal sex.

↳ Other sexual practices
– Yes
Notes: Other sexual practices apart from those legally approved, are all made prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Animals and all other creatures

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment is done on the directives of the Supreme High God.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The actual time of the eschaton is not known to any but the High God.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
 - Notes: Religion is not practiced after the eschaton.
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Paradise and Hellfire.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the attendance of five daily prayers.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 5

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 5000

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 168

Notes: The prayer is done every week.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text approved the search for wisdom.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The reward of teachers is in heaven.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?
– Yes

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– No

- ↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– Yes

Notes: The text guides the distribution of obligatory charitable donations to poor people.

- ↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?
– Yes

- ↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?
– Yes

- ↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?
– No

- ↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?
– No

- ↳ Other form of regulation of public works?
– Specify: Trade and commerce are regulated by the text.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?
– Yes

Notes: Tithe is collected from the booty of an expedition.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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